

From an initial corpus of 1,557 publications retrieved across four major academic search engines—IEEE, ACM, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar—a total of 119 primary studies were systematically selected to address eleven guiding research questions. Based on these 119 studies, we further applied backward and forward snowballing, which resulted in the identification of an additional 21 relevant papers. These studies form the foundation of our Systematic Mapping Study (SMS), presented in the research paper titled “*Mind the Attack: How Security Threats on Autonomous Drones Are Shaping Drone Software*”. The following references detail the 140 primary studies that met our inclusion criteria.

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